

PLANETARY POSITION IN CRIMINAL LAWYERS HOROSCOPE RASI CHART

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Abstract:

This paper expresses the important planetary position in criminal lawyers horoscope rasi chart.

Key Words: Mars, Saturn, Rahu, Jupiter, Mercury, Second House, Tenth House

Description of Criminal Lawyer:

The person who protects criminal and accused organizations is known as criminal lawyer. A criminal lawyer defends the persons and organizations involved in violent crimes, sexual crimes, drug trafficking (DUI) theft, disturbances, fraud (420) and domestic violence etc.... Criminal lawyer has a very prestigious service due to this reason many person want to be a criminal lawyer.

Criminal Lawyer Professional Description:

Criminal lawyers defend the accused party in criminal cases in state, federal and appellate courts in India session court District court, High court and Supreme Court. The practice of a criminal lawyer involves bail bond hearings, litigation claims cancellation hearings (parole or probation), appeals and finally punishment treatment.

Skill of Criminal Lawyer:

The work efficiency of the person is an important link for the success of any field. The defense of the accused party is important in the success of the advocate. Any kind of the crime, if the lawyer saves the accused then he is considered a good lawyer. It is very important for the lawyer to have an exploration and research skills. Criminal lawyers should also have strong creative thinking and analytical skills. The lawyer has the ability to analyze the law because it can defend the accused party on the basis of its own analysis.

How Astrology Will Help to Success as Criminal Lawyer:

It is fact that there are many Criminal lawyers in all over the world. Some are very famous personalities but some are not despite of hard working in this area. So that question come in mind, what is the reason behind this? Many students get admission in the law course for getting have degree every year. But very few students have passed. Astrologer can give you proper guidance with the help of your horoscope/ birth chart/ kundalini/zodiac sign and planetary positions in the birth chart. A person will practice as a Criminal lawyer due to the influence of Saturn and Mars. And also Rahu in 6th house or 12th house helps one to shine as the famous Criminal lawyer.

Second Bhava and Saturn:

If Saturn stands in second bhava or stand in second bhava lord's star or aspects second bhava, one should easily tell lies. It is very important to the criminal lawyer to save his accused and earn huge amount of money. Similarly the triangle of second bhava, tenth bhava is also favour for Saturn in Criminal lawyer's horoscope.

Second Bhava and Mars:

If Mars stands in second bhava or stands in Second bhava lord's star or aspects second bhava, one should easily earn money through rowdies. Because Mars refers blood (Violence) similarly the triangle of second bhava, tenth bhava is also favour for Mars in criminal lawyer's horoscope.

Mars - Saturn Conjunction:

Mars and Saturn conjunction is must for the horoscope of criminal lawyer. The following conjunctions are acceptable.

- Mars and Saturn conjunction in same house.
- Mars and Saturn stand in triangle 5/9 position.
- Mars is accepted by Saturn
- Saturn is accepted by Mars.
- Mars and Saturn exchange their house
- Mars or Moon stands in Pusam, Anusham or Uthirattathi Star
- Saturn or Moon stands in Mirigashira, Chitra or Danishta Star

- Both Mars and Saturn aspect each other by 7/7 position
- Mars stands in capricorn or Aquaris
- Saturn stands in Aries or Scorpio
- Mars or Saturn conjunction with second bhava lord.

Example Horoscope 1:

Name of the criminal lawyer : B. Thana Sekaran
 Date of Birth : 14.12,1968
 Time of birth : 17.50 pm
 Place of birth : Chennai
 Birth Star : Magam
 Kethu dhasa balance : 4 yrs 8 months 0 days

MARS SAT RAHU	10	11	12
SUN MERC	RASI		ASC
7			MOON JUPITER
VENUS	5	4	KETHU

RAHU	3	MOON	JUPITER
ASC	NAVAMSA		6
12			MARS
VENUS	SAT MERC	SUN	KETHU

MERC	SAT	7	8
SUN KETHU	DASAMSA		9
3			RAHU
MARS	ASC	JUPITER	VENUS MOON

Planet	Star
Lagna	Ayilyam 3
Sun	Danishtha 3
Moon	Magam 2
Mars	Uthratathi 1
Mercury	Danishtha 4
Jupiter	Magam 3
Venus	Uthratam 1
Saturn	Uthratathi 4
Rahu	Revathi 4
Kethu	Chitra 2

In Rasi Chart Mars and Saturn conjunctions in seventh house. Both planets stand in the star of Saturn uthrattathi. This position gave him a name as a famous criminal lawyer.

Example Horoscope 2:

Name of the criminal lawyer : K. Surenthiran
 Date of Birth : 14.07,1987
 Time of birth : 09.30 am
 Place of birth : Chennai
 Birth Star : Sathayam
 Rahu dhasa balance : 3 yrs 1 month 2 days

RAHU	JUPITER	10	SUN MERC VENUS
MOON	RASI		MARS
6			ASC
5	SATURN	3	KETHU

7	KETHU	JUPITER	SUN
VENUS MERC	NAVAMSA		11
MOON SATURN			12
4	3	MARS RAHU	ASC

SUN RAHU	3	MOON JUPITER	MARS
ASC SATURN	DASAMSAM		6
12			7

Planet	Star
Lagna	Pooram 2
Sun	Punarvasu 3
Moon	Sathayam 2
Mars	Pusam 3
Mercury	Arudra 3
Jupiter	Aswini 2

11	VENUS	MERCURY	KETHU
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Venus	Arudra 3
Saturn	Jyesta 2
Rahu	Uthrattathi 3
Kethu	Hastham 1

In rasi chart Mars and Saturn stand in 5/9 triangle position. Mars in cancer and Saturn in Scorpio. Mars stands in the star of Saturn pusam and Saturn stands in the house of Mars Scorpio. This position gave him a name as a famous Criminal lawyer

Example Horoscope 3:

Name of the criminal lawyer : R. Surenthiran
 Date of Birth : 08.08,1989
 Time of birth : 13.08pm
 Place of birth : Chennai
 Birth Star : Chitra
 Mars dhasa balance : 0 yr 0 month 20 days

5	6	7	JUPITER
RAHU	RASI		SUN
3			MARS MERCURY VENUS KETHU
SATURN			ASC MOON

8	KETHU	10	MARS
7	NAVAMSA		MERCURY
SUN			ASC SATURN
JUPITER			MOON VENUS

8	SATURN VENUS	10	MARS
RAHU	DASAMSA		12
6			ASC JUPITER KETHU
MOON			MARS MERCURY

Planet	Star
Lagna	Anuradha1
Sun	Ayilyam2
Moon	Chitra4
Mars	Magam 3
Mercury	Magam4
Jupiter	Arudra 1
Venus	Pooram 4
Saturn	Pooradam1
Rahu	Danishta 3
Kethu	Magam 1

In rasi chart Mars in tenth house, Saturn in Second house. Both stand in 5/9 triangle position. His birth star is also Mars star chitra. This position gave him a name as a famous Criminal lawyer

Example Horoscope 4:

Name of the criminal lawyer : V. VASANTHAKUMAR
 Date of Birth : 02.06,1981
 Time of birth : 11.45am
 Place of birth : Chennai
 Birth Star : Rohini
 Moon dhasa balance : 6 yrs 3 months 23 days

8	9	SUN MOON MARS	MERCURY VENUS
7	RASI		RAHU
KETHU			ASC
5			4

JUPITER SATURN	KETHU	MOON	SUN
8	NAVAMSA		ASC
7			2
MERCURY			5

5	6	MOON	VENUS RAHU
MARS	DASAMSAM		SUN

Planet	Star
Lagna	Magam 4

			JUPITER		Sun	Rohini 3
					Moon	Rohini 4
3			SATURN		Mars	Karthigai 3
					Mercury	Arudra 1
					Jupiter	Uthiram4
					Venus	Mirugasira3
KETHU	ASC	12	MERCURY		Saturn	Uthiram 4
					Rahu	Poosam 3
					Kethu	Sravanam 1

In rasi chart Mars in tenth house and Saturn in second house Both planets are in triangle. Both Saturn and Mars stand in lagna lord Sun's star. Mars in Krithigai and Saturn in Uthiram. This position gave him a name as a famous criminal lawyer.

Example Horoscope 5:

Name of the criminal lawyer : P. DEEPA
 Date of Birth : 07.03,1981
 Time of birth : 11.28 am
 Place of birth : Chennai
 Birth Star : Uthirattathi
 Saturn dhasa balance : 10 yrs11 months12 days

MOON	12	ASC	2	9	SUN	JUPITER SATURN KETHU	MARS
SUN MARS VENUS	RASI			VENUS	NAVAMSA		
MERCURY KETHU				7			
8	7	6	JUPITER SATURN	6	RAHU	4	MERCURY

9	10	11	MERCURY	Planet	Star
KETHU	DASAMSAM			Lagna	Rohini 3
7				Sun	Poorattathi 1
			RAHU	Moon	Uthirattathi 1
MOON	MARS	4	SUN JUPITER SATURN	Mars	Poorattathi 3
				Mercury	Danishta 2
				Jupiter	Hastha 2
				Venus	Sathayam 3
				Saturn	Hastham 2
				Rahu	Poosam 4
				Kethu	Sravanam 2

In rasi chart Saturn is accepted by Mars. Mars stands in Aquaris, the house of Saturn Her birth star lord is also Saturn. This position gave her a name as a famous criminal lawyer.

Example Horoscope 6:

Name of the criminal lawyer : K. RAMACHANDRAN
 Date of Birth : 17.07,1977
 Time of birth : 10.10 am
 Place of birth : Chennai
 Birth Star : Poosam
 Saturn dhasa balance : 8 yrs9 months 3 days

KETHU	8	JUPITER VENUS MARS	10	3	4	5	VENUS
6	RASI		SATURN MOON SUN MERC	SATURN MARS KETHU	NAVAMSA		SUN

5			
4	3	2	ASC RAHU

ASC			RAHU
MERCURY	11	MOON	JUPITER

SUN MARS	12	ASC	MOON VENUS
10	DASAMSA		KETHU
RAHU			4
8	7	JUPITER SATURN	MERCURY

Planet	Star
Lagna	Uthirattathi 2
Sun	Punarvasu 4
Moon	Poosam 3
Mars	Krithiga 3
Mercury	Ayilyam 1
Jupiter	Mirugasira 2
Venus	Rohini 3
Saturn	Ayilyam 3
Rahu	Chitra 1
Kethu	Revathi 3

In rasi chart Mars conjunction with second house lord Venus. The lord of his birth star is also Saturn. This position gave him a name as a famous criminal lawyer.

Example Horoscope 7:

Name of the criminal lawyer : R. VIGNESWARAN
 Date of Birth : 23.07,1989
 Time of birth : 09.20 am
 Place of birth : Chennai
 Birth Star : Uthirattathi
 Saturn dhasa balance : 17 yrs6 months1 day

MOON	9	10	JUPITER
RAHU	RASI		SUN MARS MERCURY
6			ASC VENUS KETHU
SATURN	4	3	2

MARS	KETHU	VENUS	8
4	NAVAMSA		9
2			SUN MOON SATURN
2	ASC JUPITER	MERCURY RAHU	11

RAHU	ASC	SUN SATURN	3
11	DASAMSAM		JUPITER MERCURY
10			5
MOON MARS	8	7	VENUS KETHU

Planet	Star
Lagna	Pooram 4
Sun	Poosam 1
Moon	Uthirattathi 1
Mars	Ayilyam 4
Mercury	Poosam 3
Jupiter	Mirugasira 4
Venus	Magam 2
Saturn	Pooradam 1
Rahu	Danishtha 3
Kethu	Magam 1

In rasi chart Mars is conjunction with the second house lord Mercury. His birth star is Saturn's star uthirattathi. This position gave him a name as a famous criminal lawyer.

Consolidation:

From the above seven horoscopes we can understand the importance of Mars and Saturn in criminal lawyer's horoscope. We can easily judge the horoscope rasi chart with our rules who can become the Criminal lawyer.

Conclusion:

The best help of the astrologer to the society is giving correct guidance to his/her customers. If one do it perfectly his/her clients worship them as a God.

References:

1. Jothidam Enum Maha Arputham written by Jothidakkalai Arasu Aditya Guruji. Published by Guruji Publications - Chennai, 2022.
2. Criminal lawyer description and astrology article from Google.